
168. S stars in the Wesenheit diagram

ONLY WITHIN the past century did astronomers establish that stars were powered by nucleosynthesis, and that the chemical elements (except for the very lightest: H, He, and Li) were created inside them.

The theory underpinning stellar nucleosynthesis replaced some earlier ideas that all elements were created in the Big Bang. Major conceptual advances were made in the 1940s and 1950s (Hoyle, 1946; Hoyle, 1954; Hoyle et al., 1956; Fowler et al., 1955; Burbidge et al., 1957).

Relevant to my topic of S stars is the early abstract of Fowler et al. (1955): *'It is supposed that the synthesis of the heavy elements will take place in stars which have reached the cool giant stage in their evolutionary path. The M as well as the S stars may be important in this connection.'* They estimated that... *'synthesis of the heavy elements in the S-star stage alone could account for a considerable fraction of the heavy elements'*.

STELLAR NUCLEOSYNTHESIS broadly explains why certain elements are more abundant than others, and predicts how and why they evolve over time.

The details of stellar evolution and its fusion products are not particularly simple or straightforward to interpret anywhere in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, although the reactions and internal structures of main-sequence stars are reasonably well understood. Things are more complicated for the more advanced evolutionary stages, and in particular for stars on the 'asymptotic giant branch', or AGB.

The interiors of stars on the asymptotic giant branch are characterised by a largely inert core of carbon and oxygen, an inner shell where helium is fusing to form carbon, an outer shell where H-to-He burning still operates, and an outer envelope, often of composition similar to main-sequence stars (Lattanzio & Forestini, 1999; Siess, 2006; Höfner & Olofsson, 2018; Karakas, 2019; Kobayashi et al., 2020).

Indeed, AGB stars are very important in the production of the heaviest elements. But their understanding is complicated by their dramatic and rapid evolution, and their sensitivity to the details of various crucial processes including deep mixing and strong mass loss.

AS I DESCRIBED in essay 167, a star arrives on the AGB on completion of core He-burning, where it cools, expands, and its luminosity increases. Following a series of short-duration thermal pulses (resulting from cycles of H- and He-shell burning), deep convection (the 'third dredge-up') brings He, C, and various s-process products from the core to the surface, where they are seen in the spectra and can be expelled through the stellar wind. The third dredge-up increases the C/O ratio and, in some cases, turns the star into a carbon star.

[The first dredge-up occurs when a main-sequence star enters the red-giant branch, resulting in an atmosphere displaying the products of H-fusion, including lowered $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ and C/N ratios, and lower abundances of Li and Be. The second dredge-up occurs only in intermediate-mass stars, $4 - 8M_{\odot}$. It reveals the products of the CNO cycle, increasing the surface abundance of ^4He and ^{14}N , and decreasing that of ^{12}C and ^{16}O .]

THE S STARS are cool luminous (AGB) giants lying between the O-rich M-type giants and the C-rich carbon stars. Short-lived ($10^5 - 10^6$ yr), they make up only 1% of all M stars, but their large-amplitude long-period variability facilitates their discovery. The third dredge-up also brings s-process elements to the surface, with the result that S stars show unusual absorption lines, including the defining lines of ZrO (Merrill, 1922).

In *intrinsic S stars*, the s-process elements arise from this convective dredge-up (rather than as mass-transfer in a binary system), where they are accompanied by the presence of **technetium**, another of the s-process elements. With its longest isotopic half-life of only 4.2 Myr, the presence of Tc indicates its recent creation.

To summarise, the importance of the class is that the **s-process** (slow-neutron capture) creates around half the atomic nuclei heavier than iron. A range of elements and isotopes is produced, with relative abundances depending on the source and flux of the neutrons (Suess & Urey, 1956; Clayton et al., 1961; Kobayashi et al., 2020).

The General Catalogue of Galactic S-Stars (Stenson, 1984) listed 741 stars, with one of the brightest being the 370-d, 7–14 mag Mira variable **R Gem**.

K_s versus $W(\text{Gaia}) - W(2\text{MASS})$ for (a) the LMC, (b) evolutionary models (both Lebzelter et al., 2018); (c) LAMOST (Chen et al., 2023)

MAJOR ADVANCES in understanding AGB stars have followed from large-scale multi-epoch multi-colour surveys, notably MACHO (e.g. Wood, 2003) and OGLE (e.g. Soszyński et al., 2009). Today, with its astrometry and 3-band photometry (G , BP and RP), Gaia is providing new means of identifying the various populations on the asymptotic giant branch. As we shall see, it can clearly distinguish between the O-rich and C-rich stars, as well as delineating the region populated by S stars.

Let me first explain the ‘Wesenheit function’, W . This is some combination of a star’s magnitude and colour, chosen to be (largely) unaffected by distance *and* reddening. The term comes, I believe, from the German for ‘entity’ or ‘true nature’. It was first used in the context of the Cepheid period–luminosity relation in the 1970s.

As an early proponent, Madore (1976) adopted $W = V - R(B - V)$, where R is the total-to-selective absorption ratio. The demonstrated linearity of W implies the linearity of the period–luminosity and period–intrinsic colour relations. The properties and choices for W are described further in, e.g., Ngeow & Kanbur (2005, §2).

USING THE Gaia DR2-based catalogue of 151 761 long-period variables, which itself doubled the number of known long-period variables (Mowlavi et al., 2018), Lebzelter et al. (2018) showed that a diagram of $W(\text{Gaia}) - W(2\text{MASS})$ versus K_s is a powerful tool to distinguish between different AGB classes.

Here, $W(\text{Gaia}) \equiv W_{\text{RP, BP-RP}}$ is a Wesenheit function based on the Gaia magnitudes G , G_{BP} and G_{RP} , and $W(2\text{MASS}) \equiv W_{K_s, J-K_s}$ is similarly based on the 2MASS infrared magnitudes J and K_s . Specifically, they adopted $W(2\text{MASS}) = K_s - 0.686(J - K_s)$, and $W(\text{Gaia}) = G_{\text{RP}} - 1.3(G_{\text{BP}} - G_{\text{RP}})$.

As they argued, $G_{\text{RP}} - G_{\text{BP}}$ is strongly affected by the temperature sensitivity of molecules dominating these wavelength ranges, which themselves depend on the C/O ratio. However, a degeneracy exists between interstellar reddening, circumstellar reddening, chemistry, and temperature differences at a given luminosity. By using Wesenheit functions, they could largely eliminate the interstellar reddening component (and much of the circumstellar component) from this degeneracy.

A diagram for their 11 022 Large Magellanic Cloud candidates (selected via their Gaia parallax and proper motion) is shown in the first figure. As they stress, this is not a classical colour–magnitude diagram, since the bluest objects are at the centre, with redder ones to both sides. They identified six regions (C rich, extreme C rich, O rich in three different mass ranges, and red-giant branch), and they explain how these segregations arise as a result of the different molecular species and mass ranges.

During their evolution on the AGB, stars of low and intermediate mass show strong variations of temperature, composition and luminosity on various timescales, which have been studied in detail using evolutionary models in view of their importance in stellar and Galactic evolution (e.g., Karakas & Lattanzio, 2014; Marigo et al., 2017). Their simulated populations, obtained with the TRILEGAL evolutionary code, are shown in the middle figure, well replicating the observational diagram.

THE SUBSET of S stars has been further studied using the Gaia data, providing further observational evidence for the third dredge-up, and for the detailed evolutionary status of the Tc-rich stars, based on DR2 (Shetye et al., 2018; Shetye et al., 2019; Shetye et al., 2020; Abia et al., 2020), and EDR3 (Shetye et al., 2021; Abia et al., 2022). A recent review of the field, including the most recent Gaia results, is given by Van Eck et al. (2022).

WHERE DO THE subset of S stars lie in such a Wesenheit diagram? Although I am not aware of the systematic placing of all known S stars in such a diagram on the basis of the Gaia astrometry and photometry, two specific studies provide an encouraging picture.

Figure A2 of Shetye et al. (2021) shows their 23 (spectroscopic) S stars in the same $W(\text{Gaia}) - W(2\text{MASS})$ versus K_s diagram, and most fall, as expected, in the low-mass O-rich region.

On a larger scale, Chen et al. (2023) found 2939 new S stars from LAMOST DR 10, and placed them in the same ‘Lebzelter’ diagram using Gaia DR3 astrometry and photometry. Their result, colour-coded according to whether they are inferred to be intrinsic or extrinsic, is shown top right. Again, most fall in the O-rich region.